

Analytical Evaluation of Radio-Frequency Energy-Induced Heating in a Hot Spot without perfusion

M. Kozlov¹, N. Boulant²

^{#1}Department of Neurophysics, Max Planck Institute for Human Cognitive and Brain Sciences, Leipzig, Germany

^{#2}Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, CNRS, BAOBAB, NeuroSpin, F-91191, Gif-Sur-Yvette, France.

Introduction: The specific absorption rate (*SAR*) averaged over the mass of 10 gram human tissue and over a 6 minute time (SAR_{10g}) is the primary safety limit for 7T MRI scanners [1]. SAR_{10g} is also the safety limit for multi modal study, i.e., a combination of MRI with another technique, for example transcranial electric stimulation (tES) or electroencephalography (EEG), if additional equipment is entered into the effective exposure volume of the MRI radio-frequency (RF) coil. Especially in the latter case, locations with the highest RF power deposition, i.e., hot spots, in a human body can be substantially separated in space. The dimension of volume that consists of 10 gram human tissue is 21.55 mm as cube edge or 13.365 mm as sphere radius for most human tissues. Radius of a hot spot of substantial amount of active and passive implants is in a range from 1 mm till 15 mm. Radio-frequency energy-induced heating in human tissues is a very complex process with large influence of blood perfusion that in most cases decrease the level of heating. Thus heating estimation without blood perfusion results in a conservative value. Here we provide transient analytical solutions of the temperature rise for spherically symmetric *SAR* distributions (uniform and Gaussian).

Methods: The heat diffusion equation without perfusion (as for instance the eyes) is defined as

$$k\nabla^2 T + \rho SAR = \rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

A sphere (S) of radius R enclosed in a second, infinite, sphere was considered. By symmetry, temperature only depends on the radial coordinate r if the *SAR* distribution itself is spherically symmetric.

If S is subjected to uniform *SAR* (SAR_0) and there is no *SAR* outside of S the following steady-state differential equation (heat diffusion equation in spherical coordinates) is applicable:

$$k \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \rho SAR_0 = 0 \text{ for } r \leq R \quad (2)$$

$$k \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) = 0 \text{ for } r \geq R \quad (3)$$

As it is shown in Fig. 1 the solution for this problem at $x=y=z=0$ where maximum temperature occurs is

$$T_{max} = \frac{\rho SAR_0}{2k} R^2 \quad (4)$$

This is the same as equation 17 in [2].

Analytical transient solutions in the center (maximum temperature in the sphere) likewise were obtained for uniform *SAR* by moving to the Fourier domain, integrating, and coming back to the spatial domain (Fig. 2):

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{\rho SAR_0}{k^2} R^2 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{4\alpha t}{\pi R^2}} e^{-\frac{R^2}{4\alpha t}} - \left(1 - 2 \frac{\alpha t}{R^2} \right) \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{R}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}} \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

and for a *SAR* source with a Gaussian distribution (standard deviation of σ , b is the *SAR* value at the center of the Gaussian) located in an infinite medium of homogeneous properties (Fig. 3)

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{\rho b \sigma^2}{k} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{2\alpha t}{\sigma^2}}} \right) \quad (6).$$

These analytical solutions were compared to numerical solver results and showed perfect agreement. The time ($t_{0.632}$) at which $T_{max}(t)$ will be equal to $T_{max}(t \rightarrow +\infty) \cdot (1 - e^{-1})$ for Gaussian distribution is

$$t_{0.632} = (e^2 - 1) \frac{\sigma^2}{2\alpha} \quad (7)$$

For the Gaussian case a function $T_{max}(t \rightarrow +\infty) \cdot (1 - e^{-t/\tau})$ can be used to approximate the solution at small times with a time constant $\tau = \frac{\sigma^2}{\alpha} = \frac{\rho C \sigma^2}{k} = t_{0.632} / 3.195$. Please note, however, that the exact solution is not an exponential function so that the time it takes for the temporal part to decay to e^{-1} is in fact significantly longer because of the square root dependence in Eq. 6.

Results and Discussion:

Assuming no perfusion, this work reports a conservative yet analytical evaluation of heating for uniform and Gaussian-shaped *SAR* hot spots. For uniform *SAR* of 10W/kg over 10g (13.4 mm radius sphere), and negligible *SAR* outside of S, T_{max} is 1.78 °C (reached in about 22 minutes), which is reasonable considering temperature guidelines. Under the same assumptions, one can see in Eq. 5 that the steady-state temperature also grows with R^2 , i.e. with the size of the *SAR* hotspot, and linearly with the constant SAR_0 value.

Comparison between the transient values for the Gaussian case and the uniform one is presented in Fig. 4. When the energy outside of the 10g sphere is negligible, the more peaked the *SAR* distribution, the higher T_{max} and the shorter τ . The difference between the exact analytical solution and an exponential regime with the same time-constants is highlighted in Fig. 5.

Conclusion: We showed analytically that even without taking into account blood perfusion (i) if power deposition is present only in a sphere that encloses 10 gram of human tissue and $SAR_{10g}=10W/kg$ the steady-state temperature rise is below 3 °C for power deposition distributions as sharp as Gaussian with $\sigma = R/3 = 4.45$ mm, (ii) the sharper the Gaussian distribution of power deposition, the higher $T_{max}(t \rightarrow +\infty)$ and the shorter τ are.

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Let's take equation (2):

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) = -\frac{\rho SAR_0}{k}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) = -\frac{\rho SAR_0}{k} r^2$$

$$\left(r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) = -\frac{\rho SAR_0}{3k} r^3 + A$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = -\frac{\rho SAR_0}{3k} r + \frac{A}{r^2}$$

$$T = -\frac{\rho SAR_0}{6k} r^2 - \frac{A}{r} + B \text{ for } r \leq R$$

Because temperature must be finite at $r=0$, we get $A=0$ so that $T = -\frac{\rho SAR_0}{6k} r^2 + B$ for $r \leq R$.

For $r \geq R$, $SAR=0$ so that we get: $T = -\frac{C}{r} + D$

The temperature must decay to zero at infinity so that $D=0$.

The two temperatures must be equal at $r=R$ so that: $-\frac{\rho SAR_0}{6k} R^2 + B = -\frac{C}{R}$

Equating the derivatives at $r=R$ likewise yields: $-\frac{\rho SAR_0}{3k} R = \frac{C}{R^2} \rightarrow C = -\frac{\rho SAR_0}{3k} R^3$

One therefore gets $B = -\frac{C}{R} + \frac{\rho SAR_0}{6k} R^2 \rightarrow B = \frac{\rho SAR_0}{3k} R^2 + \frac{\rho SAR_0}{6k} R^2 = \frac{\rho SAR_0}{2k} R^2$

Finally, the solution inside S is:

$$T(r) = -\frac{\rho SAR_0}{6k} r^2 + \frac{\rho SAR_0}{2k} R^2 = \frac{\rho SAR_0}{2k} \left(R^2 - \frac{r^2}{3} \right) \text{ for } r \leq R$$

The maximum temperature reached at the center ($r=0$) and in the steady-state thus is

$$T_{max} = \frac{\rho SAR_0}{2k} R^2$$

Fig. 1. Solution for steady-state temperature rise in the case of uniform SAR in a sphere.

We now use the 3D spatial Fourier Transform (FT) of T:

$$\tilde{T}(f_x, f_y, f_z, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-i2\pi(f_x x + f_y y + f_z z)} T(x, y, z, t) dx dy dz.$$

Applying this to Eq. (1) in the text yields:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial t} + \omega^2 \alpha \tilde{T} = \frac{\widetilde{SAR}}{c} \quad (1)$$

Where $\alpha = k/(\rho C)$, $\omega^2 = (2\pi f_x)^2 + (2\pi f_y)^2 + (2\pi f_z)^2 = \omega_x^2 + \omega_y^2 + \omega_z^2$ and $\widetilde{SAR}$ is the FT of SAR. Equation (1) is no longer a partial differential equation and can be solved analytically. Given that $\tilde{T}(\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z, t = 0) = 0$, one gets:

$$\tilde{T}(\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z, t) = \frac{\rho \widetilde{SAR}}{k \omega^2} (1 - e^{-\alpha \omega^2 t}). \quad (2)$$

The formula above shows that the diffusion process smooths the temperature profile by attenuating large spatial frequency components. We now go back to the spatial domain with an inverse FT:

$$T(x, y, z, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\rho \widetilde{SAR}}{k \omega^2} (1 - e^{-\alpha \omega^2 t}) e^{i2\pi(f_x x + f_y y + f_z z)} df_x df_y df_z$$

$$T(x, y, z, t) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\rho \widetilde{SAR}}{k \omega^2} (1 - e^{-\alpha \omega^2 t}) e^{i(\omega_x x + \omega_y y + \omega_z z)} d\omega_x d\omega_y d\omega_z$$

When the max occurs at x=y=z=0 (e.g. uniform SAR or Gaussian profiles centered on the origin) we have

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\rho \widetilde{SAR}}{k \omega^2} (1 - e^{-\alpha \omega^2 t}) d\omega_x d\omega_y d\omega_z. \quad (3)$$

If SAR is uniform over the sphere of radius R (SAR = b = SAR₀ for r ≤ R, 0 elsewhere) the Fourier transform of the SAR distribution is:

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{SAR} &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} SAR(x, y, z) e^{-i2\pi(f_x x + f_y y + f_z z)} dx dy dz = 2\pi b \int_0^R \int_0^\pi r^2 e^{-i2\pi f r \cos\theta} \sin\theta dr d\theta \\ &= \frac{2}{f} b \int_0^R r \sin(2\pi r) dr, \end{aligned}$$

Where $f^2 = f_x^2 + f_y^2 + f_z^2$.

After integrating by parts, one obtains: $\widetilde{SAR} = \frac{4\pi b}{\omega^3} (\sin(\omega R) - R\omega \cos(\omega R))$, where $\omega = 2\pi f$. Inserting this result into Eq. (3) and again using spherical symmetry yields:

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{\rho b}{k(2\pi)^3} (4\pi)^2 \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\omega^3} (\sin(\omega R) - R\omega \cos(\omega R)) (1 - e^{-\alpha \omega^2 t}) d\omega \quad (4)$$

After a change of variables u = ωR, the previous equation becomes:

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{2\rho b}{k\pi} R^2 \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{u^3} (\sin(u) - u \cos(u)) (1 - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{R^2} u^2 t}) du \quad (5)$$

The first part of the integral yields the steady-state and with the result

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{u^3} (\sin(u) - u \cos(u)) du = \frac{\pi}{4},$$

one recovers the steady-state result in the first part of this note: $T_{max}(t = +\infty) = \frac{\rho b}{2k} R^2 = \frac{\rho SAR_0}{2k} R^2$. Mathematica for the transient part gives $\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{u^3} (\sin(u) - u \cos(u)) e^{-au^2} du = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\pi a} e^{-\frac{1}{4a}} + \frac{1}{4} (1 - 2a) \pi \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{a}}\right)$. So the final solution for Eq. (5) is:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{max}(t) &= \frac{2\rho b}{k\pi} R^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\alpha t}{R^2}} e^{-\frac{R^2}{4\alpha t}} - \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - 2\frac{\alpha t}{R^2}\right) \pi \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{R}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}}\right) \right) \quad \text{or} \\ T_{max}(t) &= \frac{\rho b}{k2} R^2 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{4\alpha t}{\pi R^2}} e^{-\frac{R^2}{4\alpha t}} - \left(1 - 2\frac{\alpha t}{R^2}\right) \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{R}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}}\right) \right) \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 2. Solution for transient temperature rise at x=y=z=0 for a uniform SAR.

We go back to Eq. (3) of Fig. 2 which is valid for any SAR distribution spherically symmetric and peaked on the origin. We now assume the SAR distribution is a Gaussian shape

$$SAR(x, y, z) = be^{-\frac{x^2+y^2+z^2}{2\sigma^2}}$$

so that its FT is equal to $\widetilde{SAR} = b\sigma^3(2\pi)^{3/2}e^{-\omega^2\frac{\sigma^2}{2}}$. Injecting this result into (3) yields:

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{\rho b\sigma^3}{k(2\pi)^{3/2}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-\omega^2\frac{\sigma^2}{2}}}{\omega^2} (1 - e^{-\alpha\omega^2 t}) d\omega_x d\omega_y d\omega_z. \quad (1)$$

Given the symmetry of the problem, we now switch to spherical coordinates $d\omega_x d\omega_y d\omega_z = \omega^2 \sin\theta d\omega d\theta d\phi$ and first integrate over the angle coordinates:

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{\rho b\sigma^3}{k(2\pi)^{3/2}} 4\pi \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\omega^2\frac{\sigma^2}{2}} (1 - e^{-\alpha\omega^2 t}) d\omega,$$

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{\rho b\sigma^3}{k(2\pi)^{3/2}} 4\pi \left(\int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\omega^2\frac{\sigma^2}{2}} d\omega - \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\omega^2(\frac{\sigma^2}{2} + \alpha t)} d\omega \right)$$

We use the formula $\int_0^{+\infty} e^{-ax^2} dx = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{a}}$ to yield

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{\rho b\sigma^3}{k(2\pi)^{3/2}} 2\pi \left(\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\sigma^2}} - \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\sigma^2 + 2\alpha t}} \right),$$

$$T_{max}(t) = \frac{\rho b\sigma^2}{k} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{2\alpha t}{\sigma^2}}} \right) \quad (2).$$

The maximum temperature therefore approaches its steady-state as $1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{2\alpha t}{\sigma^2}}}$.

The constant b should be determined based on sphere volume V and the value of SAR averaged over the sphere (SAR_V).

$$\frac{1}{V} \int_S SAR dV = SAR_V$$

$$\frac{1}{V} \iiint be^{-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma^2}} r^2 \sin\theta dr d\theta d\phi = SAR_V,$$

$$\frac{1}{V} 4\pi \int_0^R be^{-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma^2}} r^2 dr = SAR_V,$$

After integrating by parts, one gets:

$$\frac{1}{V} 4\pi b \left(\sigma^3 \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{R}{\sigma\sqrt{2}}\right) - R\sigma^2 e^{-\frac{R^2}{2\sigma^2}} \right) = SAR_V,$$

Where erf is the error function defined as $\operatorname{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-u^2} du$.

$$b = SAR_V \frac{V}{4\pi} / \left(\sigma^3 \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{R}{\sigma\sqrt{2}}\right) - R\sigma^2 e^{-\frac{R^2}{2\sigma^2}} \right)$$

Fig. 3. Solution for transient temperature rise at $x=y=z=0$ for a SAR source with the Gaussian distribution located in an infinite medium of homogeneous properties.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Transient results at $x=y=z=0$ for a sphere of $R=13$ mm in radius for SAR averaged over the 10g sphere of 10W/kg with the Gaussian and the uniform distributions. (a) Time $t_{0.632}$ and $T_{\max}(t \rightarrow \infty)$ for different SAR distributions over the sphere. (b) Temperature rise for uniform and Gaussian distributions with $\sigma=R/2$, $\sigma=R/3$, $\sigma=R/4$, $\sigma=R/5$, $\sigma=R/6$, $\sigma=R/8$.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Comparison between exact transient temperature rise at $x=y=z=0$ for a 10g sphere of $R=13$ mm in radius for SAR averaged over the sphere of 10 W/kg and exponential regime, i.e. functions $T_{\max}(t \rightarrow +\infty)(1 - e^{-t/t_{0.632}})$ and $T_{\max}(t \rightarrow +\infty)(1 - e^{-t/\tau})$. (a) Gaussian distributions with $\sigma=R/2$. (b) Gaussian distributions with $\sigma=R/5$.

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